

Input domain modeling using Grobner bases and Lie-algebraic resolutions and implications for P vs NP

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Abstract

This article presents a novel approach to input domain modeling of some of its specific instances; those where the specifications of the function under test can be conveniently resolved into polynomial inequalities over an appropriate field. This new approach partitions the input space based on the solutions to those polynomial inequalities which can be found by computing the Grobner basis of the ideal generated by the polynomials. Another approach is a serialised version of the cellular automata that, within its own structure and granularity, partitions the input space into specific Lie-algebraic arrangement of the arguments that also satisfy the specifications. The algorithm involving Grobner bases is shown to be NP-complete and the one involving Lie-algebraic resolutions is shown to be in P. This helps one to arrive at a plausible instance that seems to be theoretically belonging to both P and NP-complete.

1 Introduction

Software testing is an activity to check the performance and correctness of the software product or service under test in the terms where it is expected to satisfy a given criteria. The given criteria is usually in the form of preconditions and postconditions in the design by contract methodology; the preconditions describe the regime of the input arguments to the software and the postconditions annotate the behaviour of the output and its evolution with time, if at all the dependence exists. Testing can be categorised into two classes based on the availability of source code: black-box testing (the one where the source code is not available to the tester) and white-box testing (the one where the source code is available). In white-box testing, the test suites are designed based on different types of criteria [10] such as fault injection, code coverage, static testing etc. Black-box testing [10, 25, 26] also has a number of approaches under its umbrella: examples include input space partitioning, boundary value analysis, all pairs testing, decision table testing etc. The methodology of interest is input space partitioning [10]; an approach which the space, from which the input values are drawn, is partitioned into disjoint sets where the inputs from the individual sets result in outputs with similar behaviour. More details about input space partitioning have been discussed in section 2, but the overall procedure is to first model the input domain in terms of the field of the valid values of the arguments and next to partition the whole space into sets of behavioral similitude. In this article, there are two approaches suggested for a specific instance of the input space partitioning problem where the specifications can be expressed in the form of polynomial inequalities. In the first approach, one can follow the lines of elimination theory [1] by considering the ideal generated by the polynomials and computing its Grobner basis [21]. The well-known algorithms to compute the Grobner basis of an ideal include Buchberger's algorithm [5] and Faugere's F_4 and F_5 algorithms [8, 9], F_5 algorithm being the fastest [22]. The problem of finding the Grobner basis has actually been showed to be reducible to an instance of the graph coloring problem [23], thus rendering it to NP-complete. In the second approach, one can actually arbitrarily partition the input domain in the way where small matrices of the input arguments are actually the members of compact Lie algebras, besides satisfying the requisite preconditions. Different Lie algebras pertain to different partitions, and the correctness of this algorithm has been shown in [24], where the whole computation has been carried out in a large cellular automata, which is further converted into a valid theory of hypothetical quanta in a physical field theory, precisely Yang-Mills theory, comprising of these Lie-algebraic symmetries. In this article, one precisely encounters a

naively serialised version of the cellular automata described in [24], which further leads to the fact that Lie-algebraic resolution of the input arguments to perform an effective input domain modeling is in P. Thus, we happen to arrive at a conjecturable yet concrete evidence of the existence of a problem that lies both in P and in NP-complete.

The rest of the article is organised in the following manner: Section 2 consolidates all the required background in the formalisms, definitions and concepts borrowed from computational algebraic geometry and software testing and verification. Section 3 discusses the use of Grobner basis to model the input domain and partition it as per specification of the function under test. Section 4 articulates the serial version of Lie-algebraic input space partitioning elucidated in [24] and formulates the existence of a problem both in P and NP. Section 5 concludes the article.

2 Background

We begin with some preliminary definitions of the mathematical, precisely algebro-geometric, tools that we use to describe the algorithm in section 3. I will be borrowing them from [1]. A monomial in variables $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ is a product of the form $x_1^{\alpha_1} x_2^{\alpha_2} x_3^{\alpha_3} \dots x_n^{\alpha_n}$ where all the indices $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ are all non-negative. The sum $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \dots + \alpha_n$ associated to the monomial $x_1^{\alpha_1} x_2^{\alpha_2} \dots x_n^{\alpha_n}$ is known as its total degree. We will sometimes resort to a shorthand notation $\vec{x}^{\vec{\alpha}}$ where $\vec{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$ and $\vec{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$. A polynomial f in x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with coefficients in a field \mathbb{K} is a finite linear combination (with coefficients in \mathbb{K}) of monomials,

$$f = \sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} x^{\alpha}, a_{\alpha} \in \mathbb{K}$$

where the sum is over a finite number of such vectors $\vec{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$. The set of all polynomials in x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n with coefficients in \mathbb{K} is denoted as $\mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$. Also, given a field \mathbb{K} and a positive integer n , we define an n -dimensional affine space over \mathbb{K} as the set

$$\mathbb{K}^n = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) : a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{K}\}$$

For the field \mathbb{K} and the polynomials $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_s \in \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, the set,

$$\mathbf{V}(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_s) = \{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in \mathbb{K}^n : f_i(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = 0, \forall 1 \leq i \leq s\}$$

is known as the affine variety defined by f_1, f_2, \dots, f_s . An ideal is a subset $I \subset \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ if satisfies

1. The zero polynomial is in I .
2. If $f, g \in I$, then $f + g \in I$.
3. If $f \in I$ and $h \in \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, then $hf \in I$.

As an example, for polynomials $f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_s$ in $\mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, the set,

$$\langle f_1, f_2, \dots, f_s \rangle = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^s h_i f_i : h_1, h_2, \dots, h_s \in \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] \right\}$$

is known as an ideal. It has been stated and proven in [1] that, for an affine variety $V \in \mathbb{K}^n$, then the set,

$$\mathbf{I}(V) = \{f \in \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] : f(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = 0, \forall (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in V\}$$

is also an ideal, precisely known as ideal of the affine variety V . A monomial ordering on $\mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ is any relation $>$ on the set of the monomials $\vec{x}^{\vec{\alpha}}$, $\vec{\alpha} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$, satisfying:

1. $>$ is a total (or linear ordering) on $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$.
2. If $\alpha > \beta$ and $\gamma \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$, then $\alpha + \gamma > \beta + \gamma$.
3. $>$ is a well-ordering on $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$. This means that every non-empty subset of $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$ has a smallest element under $>$.

For a nonzero polynomial $\sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} x^{\alpha} \in \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n]$ and a monomial order $>$, the following are defined.

1. The multidegree of f is

$$\text{multideg}(f) = \max(\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n: a_{\alpha} \neq 0)$$

2. The leading coefficient of f is $LC(f) = a_{\text{multideg}(f)} \in \mathbb{K}$.
3. The leading monomial of f is $LM(f) = x^{\text{multideg}(f)}$.
4. The leading term of f is $LT(f) = LC(f)LM(f)$.

An ideal $I \subset \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ is a monomial ideal if there is a subset $A \subset \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^n$ (possibly infinite) such that I consists of all polynomials which are finite sums of the form $\sum_{\alpha \in A} h_{\alpha} x^{\alpha}$, where $h_{\alpha} \in \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$. Again, it has been stated and proven in [1] that for an ideal $I \subset \mathbb{K}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, $\langle LT(I) \rangle$ is a monomial and there exist $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_t \in I$ such that $\langle LT(I) \rangle = \langle LT(g_1), LT(g_2), \dots, LT(g_t) \rangle$. This subset $\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_t\} \subset I$ is known as the Grobner basis. Computation of Grobner bases is useful in solving systems of polynomial equations, solving the implicitization problem, solving the ideal membership problem [1], signal and image processing [2], robotics [3], cryptography [4], etc.

Apart from the monomial order, there are several other orderings of computational relevance. Lexicographic order (lex) first compares exponents of x_1 in the monomials, and in case of equality compares exponents of x_2 , and so forth. Graded lexicographic order (grlex) first compares the total degree (sum of all exponents), and in case of a tie applies lexicographic order. Graded reverse lexicographic order (grevlex) compares the total degree first, then uses a reverse lexicographic order as tie-breaker, but it *reverses the outcome* of the lexicographic comparison so that lexicographically larger monomials of the same degree are considered to be grevlex smaller.

Software testing is a process where one checks, by actual execution, whether a given program is correct or not, given one knows the correct results to all the possible inputs to the program [10]. This differs from verification, where one mathematically proves the correctness of a program! There have been several approaches to systematically test programs [10] such as coverage criteria (graph coverage, logic coverage), syntax-based criteria, regression-based techniques, etc. One such approach of interest is input space partitioning, where one looks at the input space or domain (the set of all possible inputs to the program) and partitions it into complete and disjoint subsets [10], mainly with the intention of picking one or more test cases from each partition, so that with that small selection of test cases, one can guarantee the correctness of any other test case in the corresponding partition. Taking a decision on partitioning of the input domain is known as input domain modeling [10].

1. Interface-based input domain modeling, where the input or the interface is usually a set of arguments, and each individual argument is considered in isolation while partitioning the input domain.
2. Functionality-based input domain modeling, where the actual characteristics of the system under test are considered for deciding on partitions.

The input domain modeling has been studied in detail using time domain-based techniques [11], combinatorial techniques [12], model complexity-based analyses [13], with applications into fields such as financial mathematics [14]. Some generic types of input space partitioning include equivalence partitioning [15], boundary value testing [15], category partitioning [16], domain testing [17], classification trees [18], and many others [19, 20]. Once we model the input space and partition it into the desired domains, we pick up one or more test cases (a handful of them) randomly from each partition to test for the correctness of the system. The interesting part of the algorithm discussed in section 3 is that it converts the formal specification of the system's behaviour into a system of polynomial equations, uses elimination theory to reduce it to a problem of finding the Grobner basis, and then automatically partition the input space of the arguments to the system into the zones decided by the resulting inequalities. Then the test cases are randomly drawn from these partitions.

3 Input domain modeling using Grobner bases of the specification

For any program or a computable function that is to be formally verified, the specifications consist of the preconditions that the input arguments need to satisfy, and the postconditions that decide the way the output(s) is(are) expected to behave. It is convenient to assume a model where both the preconditions and the postconditions are expressed using first-order logic composed of terms and well-defined formulae formed from those terms. The terms are basically some functions of the input variables. For this article, we deal with only polynomials of the input variables, and the variables that take values from a field only. Examples of fields include $\mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$ (p being prime), \mathbb{Q} , \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{C} etc. Variables having values from fields such as \mathbb{Q} , \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} are easily realisable in modern-day high-level programming languages such as C/C++, Python, Java etc., although the precision practically used to store reals as floating-point numbers in a memory device eclipses \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} to realise \mathbb{Q} and $P = \{p + \iota q : p, q \in \mathbb{Q}\}$ respectively. Well, more advanced data types can also be mapped to the set of integers very easily. A trivial example is the set $\mathbb{Z}^n = \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z} \times \dots \times \mathbb{Z}$ can be proven to be isomorphic to \mathbb{Z} . Any formal language can be mapped to the set of integers in the following way: the alphabet $\Sigma = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ is mapped to the set $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ through the invertible function $f: \Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, where $f(a_k) = k - 1, 1 \leq k \leq n$, and then any string $h \in \Sigma^*$, $h = p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_n$ can be mapped to the sum

$$r_h = \sum_{k=1}^n f(p_k) n^{k-1}$$

For example, $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$ can be mapped to $\mathbb{Z}/3\mathbb{Z} = \{0, 1, 2\}$ via a map r , $r(a) = 0, r(b) = 1, r(c) = 2$, and the regular language $a(b+c)^*$ would represent all the positive integers divisible by 3. As another example, $\Sigma = \{a, b\}$ can be mapped to $\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z} = \{0, 1\}$ via the map $r: \Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z}$, $r(a) = 0, r(b) = 1$, and the context-free language $L = \{a^n b^n : n \geq 1\}$ would represent the integers of the form $r_{a^n b^n} = 2^n(2^n - 1)$. The preconditions and postconditions are then easy to be interpreted in terms of polynomial inequalities.

Polynomial equations [1] and inequalities [2] can be solved using the Grobner bases of the polynomials involved. Once the polynomial inequalities are solved for n variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , there are $2n$ regimes, n regimes for different variables that satisfy the polynomial inequalities and the other n regimes that don't. This way, roughly, there can be 2^n different ways of choosing test cases, only one of which actually satisfy the specifications. Indirectly, polynomial inequalities in n variables produces $O(\exp(n \log(c)))$ partitions, $c \in \mathbb{R}$. Buchberger's algorithm [5] was the first attempt to automate the computation of Grobner basis using the multivariate reduction of the Syzygy polynomials [1]. A parallelised version of the implementation of the algorithm has also been presented in [6]. Dube [7] proved that this algorithm takes asymptotically doubly-exponential time, precisely $d^{2^{\Omega(n)}}$ time, n being the number of variables and d being the maximal total degree of the polynomials involved. One bottleneck in the multivariate reduction in Buchberger's algorithm is the consideration of all possible pairs of the input polynomials. Faugere [8], at first, optimised on the choice of the pairs with a notion known as the "critical pair" and came up with the F_4 algorithm. Although the average-case complexity improves significantly by some improvement, the asymptotic complexity remains the same [8]. To improve further, Faugere optimised upon the "trivial syzygies" and the F_5 algorithm [9] just considers these and discards away the non-trivial ones. The complexity of the F_5 algorithm is decided by the following theorem:

Theorem 1. *Let (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m) be a system of homogeneous polynomials of identical degree $\delta \geq 2$ in $k[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ with $m > n - l$ and $l \geq 0$, with respect to which (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) are in simultaneous Noether position. Then the number of arithmetic operations in k to compute a Grobner basis for the grevlex order is bounded by a function of δ, l, n that behaves asymptotically as*

$$B(\delta)^n n \left(A(\delta, l) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \right), n \rightarrow \infty$$

where l and δ are $O(1)$. There, the coefficients $B(\delta)$ and $A(\delta, l)$ are given by

$$B(\delta) = \frac{\lambda_0^2(\lambda_0 + 1)^2}{2\lambda_0 + 1} \left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_0} \right)^{2\delta} - 1 \right)$$

$$A(\delta, l) = \frac{1}{2\pi(1 + \lambda_0)^{1+l}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\delta} \right) \left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda_0} \right)^3 - 1 \right)$$

, λ_0 being the unique positive root between $\frac{\delta-1}{2}$ and $\delta-1$,

$$\left(\frac{\lambda + 1}{\lambda} \right)^{2\delta} = \frac{1}{1 - \delta \cdot \left(\frac{2\lambda + 1}{3\lambda^2 + 3\lambda + 1} \right)}$$

Maybe the worst-case exponential time complexity is reminiscent of the fact that computing the Grobner basis is in NP-complete; it has been shown that k -colorizability of a graph G is equivalent to the condition that the constant polynomial $1 \in I_{G,k}$ for a certain ideal $I_{G,k}$ [23]. Precisely, for a graph $G = (V, E)$, $|V| = n$, and k colors $C_k = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k\}$, the ideal $I_{G,k}$ is given as,

$$I_{G,k} = I_{n,k} + \langle x_i^{k-1} + x_i^{k-2}x_j + x_i^{k-3}x_j^2 + \dots + x_j^{k-1}; (i, j) \in E \rangle, I_{n,k} = \{x_i^k - 1; i \in V\}$$

In conclusion, the input domain modeling using Grobner basis of the polynomials in a specification with variables coming from a field has been actually shown to be NP-complete. In the section 4, we would try to obtain a serial version of the Lie-algebraic input space partitioning that uses first-order two-dimensional cellular automata [24].

4 Serialised Lie-algebraic input domain modeling

In [24], a scheme was proposed for parallelised Lie-algebraic input domain modeling (IDM) using first-order two-dimensional cellular automata (CA); “automated input domain modeling with randomised test case generation in a classification tree adhering to some Lie-algebraic structures using a scalable parallelised framework of first-order two-dimensional cellular automata cellular automata that encompasses a large number of test cases simultaneously”. CAs facilitate data parallelism and simultaneity but does instill a space-time tradeoff; the parallelised IDM takes $O(m^2)$ time and $O(m^2)$ space for a function f that takes m arguments. There is a small modification to be considered now; the input arguments from the input space should actually adhere to the specifications. The serialised version of the same is sketched in algorithm 1, which chooses arguments from the groups $\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F})$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F})$ and $\mathfrak{sp}(2n, \mathbb{F})$ which are defined for a field \mathbb{F} as follows: $\mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) = \{A: A \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}, \text{tr}(A) = 0\}$, $\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}) = \{A: A \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}, A^T = -A\}$, and $\mathfrak{sp}(2n, \mathbb{F}) = \{A: A \in \mathbb{F}^{2n \times 2n}, \Omega A + A^T \Omega = 0\}$, $\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & I_n \\ -I_n & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, I_n being the $n \times n$ identity matrix. Here, the set $\mathfrak{gl}(n, \mathbb{F}) = \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}$ has all the $n \times n$ matrices with elements borrowed from the field \mathbb{F} . The proof of correctness of algorithm or the cellular automata in [24] is inspired from some notions in quantum field theory of hypothetical quanta.

Algorithm 1

Input: The function f under test which takes m arguments from the field \mathbb{F} , the precondition P and the postcondition Q

Output: A boolean answer whether f under the precondition P satisfies Q or not.

1. Choose a positive integer n such that $(n-1)^2 < m \leq n^2$.
2. $k = 8$ if $n \bmod 2 = 0$ else $k = 4$
3. Choose another positive integer d such that $(d-1)^2 < kn^4 \leq d^2$.
4. Declare 2 two-dimensional matrices W and X of size $d \times d$.

5. If n is odd, the 4 partitions of the input domain model are $\mathfrak{gl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}))^c$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F})^c$, $\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F})^c$ and $\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F})$.
6. If n is even, the 8 partitions of the input domain model are $\mathfrak{gl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap (\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F}))^c$, $\mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap (\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}))^c$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap (\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}))^c$, $\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap (\mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F}))^c$, $\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F})^c$, $\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F})^c \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F})$ and $\mathfrak{sp}(n, \mathbb{F})^c \cap \mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{F}) \cap \mathfrak{so}(n, \mathbb{F})$.
7. Choose km matrices randomly from the k partitions changing m arguments individually (that satisfy the precondition P) and patch them up in the matrix W .
8. $\forall 1 \leq i, j \leq d, X[i, j] = f(W[i, j], \{W[(i+a) \bmod d, (j+b) \bmod d]: W[(i+a) \bmod d, (j+b) \bmod d] \text{ is an argument in the patched matrix.}\})$.
9. Return the truth value of $\forall 1 \leq i, j \leq d, X[i, j]$ satisfies Q .

The worst-case complexity of the serialised Lie-algebraic input modeling algorithm is $O(\Delta m^2)$ where m is the number of arguments to the function and Δ is the longest possible time taken to randomly choose the arguments from the input partitions to satisfy the precondition. The constant Δ could be fairly large depending on the randomness of the values being chosen from the field, but is independent of m , whatsoever. So definitely, the serialised Lie-algebraic input modeling lies in P, as long as Δ does not necessarily exponentially depend on m .

So in section 3 and this, the same problem of modeling the input domain/space has been solved in two ways: modeling the input space by resolving the specification of the program into polynomial inequalities over the appropriate field and then computing the Grobner basis using F_5 algorithm; and resolving the input space into partitions where the arguments ought to satisfy some specific Lie algebras and also satisfy the preconditions, and then checking these partition spaces evolving with the help of the test function satisfy the postconditions. The former has been theoretically shown to be in NP-complete and the latter has been shown to be in P. So, an instance of a problem that hypothetically lies in both NP and P could plausibly be the problem of modeling the input domain of a program whose preconditions and postconditions can be expressed in the form of polynomial inequalities. Since the computation of Grobner basis has been shown to be able to be reduced to an instance of the graph colouring problem [23], the approach thus arrived could have some sequences to show that the graph colouring problem could also lie both in NP and P.

5 Conclusion

This article discusses a novel approach towards a standard problem of automating the process of input domain modeling: one where the input space is partitioned into disjoint sets of instances, each of which has a different response. This new approach considers instances where the preconditions and postconditions can be resolved into polynomial inequalities over a suitable field compatible with the 'type' of the arguments to the function under test. These inequalities are solved using the Grobner basis of the ideal generated by the polynomials. This approach can be easily shown to be in NP-complete. An alternate algorithm has also been suggested which is really just a serialisation of the cellular automata discussed in [24]. Now this algorithm merely partitions the input space into sets where the inputs to the function under test are resolved into matrices that satisfy certain Lie algebra, randomly chosen to satisfy the imposed preconditions as well. These matrices are patched up into one single large matrix which is later scanned to be satisfying the postconditions as well. The 'large' matrix is of the polynomial order of the number of inputs to the function. This naturally presents to us an instance of a problem which appears to be both in P as well as NP-complete. It would be interesting to see in future if there are some other intuitional and algebraically verifiable instances of input domain modeling algorithms which seem to convincingly fall in the same category. At a more fundamental level, it will be more interesting to see if the some generic class of instances of the graph colouring problem can also be solved in P, as the computation of the Grobner basis can be shown to be reducible to the same. Thus, the findings presented in this article put forth some really prospective implications for the P vs NP problem.

6 References

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